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MODERN PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES TO TEACHING FOREIGN
LANGUAGES (ENGLISH LANGUAGE): A COMPETENCY-BASED PERSPECTIVE

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Annotation. Today, students learn a foreign language faster through modern methods and various interactive games than through traditional methods. This article describes the effectiveness of competency-based pedagogical approaches in teaching a foreign language. The study focuses on the importance of modern information technologies in the educational process and the role of didactic materials and multimedia tools in developing language learners' mental competencies, i.e., knowledge of language theories, national culture, and intercultural communication skills tools.

Keywords: traditional style, competence, modern style, interactive methods, foreign languages, multimedia

Annotatsiya. Bugungi kunda o'quvchilar chet tilini an'anaviy usullardan ko'ra zamonaviy usullar va turli interaktiv o'yinlar orqali tezroq o'rganmoqdalar. Ushbu maqolada xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda kompetensiyaviy yondashuvlarning samaradorligi tavsiflangan. Tadqiqotda zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalarining ta'lim jarayonidagi ahamiyati va til o'rganuvchilarning aqliy kompetensiyalarini, ya'ni til nazariyalari, milliy madaniyat va madaniyatlارaro muloqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda didaktik materiallar va multimedia vositalarining o'rni masalasiga e'tibor qaratilgan

Kalit so'zlar: ananaviy uslub, kompetensiya, zamonaviy uslub, interaktiv metodlar, xorijiy tillar, multimedia vositalari

Аннотация. Сегодня учащиеся изучают иностранный язык быстрее современными методами и различными интерактивными играми, чем традиционными методами. В данной статье описана эффективность компетентностных педагогических подходов в

преподавании иностранных языков. В исследовании основное внимание уделяется значению современных информационных технологий в образовательном процессе и роли дидактических материалов и мультимедийных средств в развитии ментальных компетенций, то есть знаний языковых теорий, национальной культуры и навыков межкультурной коммуникации у изучающих язык.

Ключевые слова: традиционный стиль, компетенция, современный стиль, интерактивные методы, иностранные языки, мультимедийные средства

Introduction

Today, learning a foreign language is becoming a requirement of the times, therefore the majority of foreign language learners are young people. Teaching methods include not only methods, but also how to organize learning activities. And any method can be chosen for learning, it all depends on the goals he wants to achieve. Sometimes a certain method is required to achieve success in education, while others are ineffective, the methodology of organizing training in vocational education was studied by Khodjaboyev, Sh. Kasimov and others. Unlike traditional methodology, modern methodology is much more student-centered. [3] According to Jim Scrivener, the teacher's main role is to "help learning to happen," which includes

"involving" students in what is going on "by enabling them to work at their own speed, by not giving long explanations, by encouraging them to participate, talk, interact, do things, etc." [4] Broughton adds that "the language student is best motivated by practice in which he senses the language is truly communicative, that it is appropriate to its context, that his teacher's skills are moving him forward to a fuller competence in a foreign language" [2]. According to Jim Scrivener, the teacher's main role is to "help learning to happen," which includes "involving" students in what is going on "by enabling them to work at their own speed, by not giving long explanations, by encouraging them to participate, talk, interact, do things, etc." [4]. In Uzbekistan, many reforms have been carried out since 2012. Note that within the framework of the implementation of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and the National Program for Personnel Training, a comprehensive system for teaching foreign languages has been created in the country, aimed at forming a harmoniously developed, educated, modern-thinking young generation, and further integration of the republic into the world community. During the years of independence, more than 51.7 thousand foreign language teachers have been trained, multimedia textbooks in English, German, and French for grades 5-9 of general education schools, electronic resources for learning English in primary grades have been prepared, and more than 5 thousand language labs have been equipped in general education schools, vocational colleges, and academic lyceums. At the same time, analysis of the current system of organizing foreign language learning shows that educational standards, curricula, and textbooks do not fully meet modern requirements, in particular, the need to use advanced information and media technologies. Education is conducted mainly in traditional methods. The organization of continuous study of foreign languages at all levels of the education system, as well as improving the qualifications of teachers and providing them with modern teaching materials, requires further improvement [1]. Currently, in accordance with the Law, the introduction of digital technologies and innovative pedagogical approaches in foreign language teaching is becoming a priority area of modern education. The rules used in the grammatical and speech process, which students find difficult to learn and apply in practice, are visualized using modern information and communication technologies (ICT), interactive multimedia resources, online platforms, and artificial intelligence applications. As a result, this allows for capturing students' attention and transforming their theoretical knowledge into practical skills. Innovative approaches such as problem-based learning, project-based learning, gamification, and blended learning transform students from passively listening to content into active researchers. The purpose of the research is to analyze the possibilities of digital tools in increasing the effectiveness of teaching mental competencies in foreign language lessons, i.e., knowledge of language theories, culture of the country, intercultural communication skills, and to propose modern lesson models. Rational use of various interesting activities serves to develop students' grammatical competence along with increasing their information literacy. Improving the ability to consciously acquire skills learned in various speech situations. Indeed, it is an effective way to convey the great possibilities

for a foreign language to the younger generation in an understandable and attractive way with various methods.

Methodology

At the initial stage of the study, curricula and textbooks on a foreign language, in particular, English, on the topic "Weather," were analyzed from the point of view of digital didactics. A

comparative description of lesson developments was developed based on the integration of traditional lesson models and modern methods. Blended Learning and Flipped Classroom models were selected as innovative approaches. Within the framework of these models, it was methodologically substantiated that theoretical information is presented to students before the lesson through digital resources (video lessons, spreadsheets), and classes are devoted only to practical analysis and problem tasks. Pedagogical experiment was conducted in English lessons of secondary schools selected for testing. Multimedia dictionaries, thematic videos, gamification technologies were introduced in the experimental groups. In the control groups, classes were conducted according to the current traditional methodology. To ensure the objectivity of the research, the level of students' grammatical competence was checked at the beginning of the lesson (pre-test) and at the end of the lesson (post-test) using specially developed diagnostic tasks. The obtained results were processed using mathematical and statistical methods. The analysis examined not only the indicators of students' mastery, but also their activity in independent work with the help of interesting methodological activities, the ability to apply the rules of the existing point in various situations, and interest in the subject. The research methodology lesson serves to be interesting and useful in accordance with the standards.

Result

Statistical data obtained from pedagogical experiments and integrated lessons showed the following results:

The level of student assimilation: The quality of assimilation of the topic in the experimental groups at the end of the experiment averaged 85%. Compared to the control groups, their indicator was 68-75%.

Skill formation: the level of error-free completion of tasks on the topic increased by 23% in the experimental group. Especially with the help of digital tests (Kahoot, Wordwall), high accuracy was achieved in understanding the differences in the meanings of words related to the topic.

Time management: The time spent explaining the new topic using modern methods and didactic materials averaged 15 minutes. Twice as fast as the time spent on the theoretical part of the previous traditional teaching method. In the time saved, the volume of practical classes based on the task based method, aimed at developing students' speech competencies, was increased by 45%.

Involvement indicator: When using gamification technologies, 100% of students in the class were interested and involved in the lesson process.

Discussion

The research results confirmed that the use of digital technologies and modern methods in foreign language lessons, in particular, in English lessons, is not only a way to increase visual appeal, but also a factor in the quality of education and the development of many language competencies of students.

Firstly, problem-based learning and the combined use of various platforms in teaching foreign languages strengthen the learner's logical memory. If the student memorizes the rule in the traditional way, they can visually analyze the meaning of words and language competencies in the digital environment.

Secondly, the provision of interesting tasks through digital platforms within the framework of the "Blended" educational approach will contribute to healthy competition among students and the development of self-assessment skills.

In this method, the teacher moves from the main instructor's position to the facilitator's position.

Thirdly, as a result of discussions among students, digital resources and materials raise students' ability to analyze situations to a conscious level. Students begin to correctly choose parts of speech according to speech situations, which directly serves the ultimate goal of education - the formation of literate speech.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the success of the competency-based approach in teaching foreign languages directly depends on the combination of digital technologies and modern methods. Digital tools

(artificial intelligence, multimedia platforms, mobile applications) move the educational process away from traditional patterns and bring it closer to a real communication environment. This forms not only linguistic knowledge in students, but also communicative, social, and information competencies necessary for the 21st century.

Today, the modern teacher should not only provide knowledge, but also act as a guide (facilitator) in the digital world. Systematic use of digital resources and constant updating of teaching methods to improve the quality of education in the future will undoubtedly bring foreign language proficiency indicators to a new level.

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4. An annotation of 60 words in the next line in three languages.
5. Key words from the next row in three languages 7-10.
6. The next line begins with the main text. The main text begins on the next line, and the article consists of four parts: the relevance of the topic, the methods and level of research, the results, and the conclusion.
7. Articles must be of scientific importance and facts and opinions in the article should be well-grounded and have an independent meaning, and they must be free of plagiarism. The author must clearly demonstrate the literature used in his or her opinion, and provide the exact sources of the extracts.
8. Quotes should be from "Web of science" and "Scopus" journals.
9. A complete list of publications should be followed in alphabetical order after the main text. Seals and references should be in the main text [1, 25].